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AN INVENTORY ON THE ROLE AND CHALLENGES OF THE EFCC IN THE FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION IN NIGERIA

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17021755](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17021755)

Abstract

The Nigerian legislation has always favoured the jurisdiction of the Nigerian police in matters appertaining to crime and criminal investigations. However, the economic and global effect of cyber development has created crevice in the ordinary nature of crime and criminal activities, inclusive of crimes such as cybercrimes, economic and financial crimes, money laundering, and etcetera. Oftentimes and most times, the criminal activities concomitant to internet regime has operated to affect the economic and financial development of the country. Sadly enough, the threshold pillar harbouring the development of this new set of criminal activities remain the internet regime, which portends a negative impact on socio-economic development, international banking and financial growth. The sophistication associated with this trend requires a well-trained department conversant in information communication technology. This has given rise to the establishment of the economic and financial crimes commission. Consequent on the above, the author strived to unravel the role and challenges of the EFCC within the economy as well as in juxtaposition to the e-administration and e-governance developmental structure of the country. The paper therefore argued that arresting incidental criminal harvest and menaces associated with the internet regime required a critical consideration of the role and challenges of the EFCC in Nigeria. The author maintained the need to checking the subsisting ‘effort-fatigue’ of the EFCC.

Keywords: cybercrime, criminal activities, economic activities, financial development, developmental efforts.

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1. Introduction

The prosecution of criminal cases is one of the responsibilities assigned to the police in Nigeria. The police power of prosecution is only subject to the overriding prosecution power of the Attorney-General of the Federation or the State.¹ However, the issue of investigating and prosecution of economic and financial crimes were later vested on the EFCC. The EFCC Act also empowers the commission to prosecute corporate financial crimes in Nigeria, which effort has captured ascertaining the determinants of corporate financial crimes in Nigeria; to investigate the economic implication of corporate financial crimes in Nigeria; as well as to examine the effectiveness of EFCC in prosecuting generally, corruption cases as well as corporate financial crimes in Nigeria.² In fact, there is no gainsaying the fact that issues regarding corporate financial crimes are getting more prominent among the public, especially investors, investment managers and also regulators. Corporate financial crime is a serious crime that relates to ethical behaviour which should not be taken lightly, as it does not only have deep impact on the reputation of the company affected, but also causes greater financial loss and loss of investors' confidence.³

Corruption has been a major societal problem in the 21st century. It is prevalent in developing countries as well as in the developed ones. During the 1980s and 1990s, major banking frauds and corruption scandals occurred in many countries. Nigeria has experienced its fair share of such scandals, especially during the military era and even in her current democratic dispensation.⁴ The impact of corruption on our national economy has manifested in different kinds of political, social, and economic vices. This led to the formation of the EFCC by the President Obasanjo administration to find ways of tackling and eradicating corruption in our society.⁵

The jurisdiction of the EFCC covers principally economic and financial crimes in Nigeria. Significantly, financial crimes extend to corporate crimes, ordinarily referred to as white collar crimes. Furthermore, the commission is mandated to combat corruption within the political circle, that is, corruption involving both economic and financial crimes. There are avalanche of cases

¹ Okpako Omudhowo & Anya Kingsley Anya, Exercise of Police prosecutorial powers under the Police Act, KB Law Scholars Journal UK, 1(6), 91-100, <<https://doi.org/10.60787/kblsj.v1i6.56>> accessed 31/07/25

² Uchegbu Callista Ukamaka & Kelvin Ibobo, The Role of the EFCC in prosecuting corporate financial crimes in Nigeria, Journal of Contemporary Issues in Accounting (JOCIA) Vol. 1 No. 1 April, 2021 <<https://journals.unizik.edu.ng/jocia>> accessed 27/07/25

³ Ibid, at p. 147

⁴ Paul Chibuike Ezebuilo, Economic and Financial Crimes Commission and Political Corruption in Nigeria (2007 -2015) <https://covenantuniversity.academia.edu/121.293227>

⁵ Ibid.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17021755

determined by the commission involving government officials and political leaders.⁶ Closely connected to cybercrime, financial crimes are often committed via the internet and have a major impact on international banking and financial sectors-both official and alternative. Financial crimes affect private individuals, companies, organizations, and even nations, and have a negative impact on the economic and social system through the considerable loss of money.

Prior to the enactment of the Act of 2002 as amended by the EFCC Act 2004 there was no comprehensive definition of what constituted a financial crime. Significantly, section 46 defined financial crime as a nonviolent criminal unlawful action concerned with the objective of earning wealth illegally either individually or a group or organized manner thereby violating existing legislation governing the financial actions of a government and its administration and includes any forms of fraud such as: money laundering, embezzlements, bribery, looting and any form of corrupt malpractices, illegal arms deal, smuggling, human trafficking and child labour, illegal oil bunkering, theft of intellectual property and piracy, open market abuse, dumping of toxic waste and prohibited good.⁷ This statutory definition reveals that the crime could reasonably include a wide variety of criminal offences.⁸ It has been argued that corruption has been part of Nigerian existence for 39 years of military rule after independence in 1960.⁹ The desire of stealing public treasury, decapitated public institutions and free speech restrictions led to secrecy in the running of affairs of government. The outcome was a complete insecurity, poor economics management, abuse of human rights and ethnic conflicts.

The paper therefore examined the associated intricacies involved in the affairs of the EFCC taking into consideration, the role of the EFCC in the socio-economic development of the country; the challenges of the EFCC and thereafter, the conclusion.

2. The role of the EFCC in the socio-economic development of Nigeria

Corruption is one of the greatest threats to economic and political development of any nation. Therefore, the challenges of fighting corruption remain a major devastating issue facing Nigeria right from the colonial period. It has become a cankerworm that has eaten deep into the fabrics of

⁶ Dr Martin Okonta, Legal and Administrative development of plea bargain in criminal justice in Nigeria, KB Law Scholars Journal UK, 3(1), 1-23, <<https://10.5281/zenodo.15796818>> accessed 30/07/25

⁷ Economic and financial crimes commission [Hereafter, the EFCC Act 2004]

⁸ (Establishment Act, 2004)

⁹ Mallam Nuhu Ribadu, (then Chairman of the EFCC) An address to the US congressional house committee on international development (2006)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17021755

our system. Corruption is both a socio-economic and political menace. The stark realities associated with corruption has been captured and reflected through legislative process thus giving birth to the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission Act of 2004. The effectiveness or ineffectiveness of the EFCC Act is largely dependent on the exercise of political will on the part of the Executive in prosecuting corruption related offences not minding whose ox is gored.

The issue of corruption has as a matter of fact, coupled with the activities of corrupt public officials, individuals in private sectors and bad-governance by political leaders, continue to led to loss of confidence in Nigeria by its citizens at home and abroad. And on the international scene, Nigeria has been blacklisted as a State in which integrity and transparency are alien and, where no transaction occurs without gratification.¹⁰

Nevertheless, resolving solutions to corruption rests in our hands and cannot be put off to another day. That is why many countries have put in place different mechanisms for checkmating the spate of corruption. In Nigeria for example, the menace of corruption has been discussed at different levels. Notwithstanding the efforts made, incidents of corruption keep surviving at all facets of human endeavour.¹¹

Since the return of the country to civil rule on May 29, 1999 the Nigerian government has taken a number of measures to address the problem of corruption and bad governance in the country. These measures include public service reform, and the establishment of anti-corruption legislations. Despite the success attained by these measures, the situation remains unacceptable as corruption continues to permeate and pervade every facet of our national life.

This Act is one of the principal anti-corruption legislations in Nigeria. It was considered to have a limited coverage, thus it was necessary to have laws to prevent economic and financial criminality.

The Act provides in S 6 that: That the Commission shall be responsible for:

- A. The enforcement and the due administration of the provision of this Act. The investigation of all financial crimes including advanced fee fraud, money laundering, counterfeiting, illegal charge transfers, futures market fraud, fraudulent enhancement of negotiable instruments, computer credit card fraud, contract scam, and etcetera,
- B. The co-ordination and enforcement of all economic and financial crimes laws and enforcement functions conferred on any other person or authority.
- C. The adoption of measures to identify, trace, freeze, confiscate or seize proceed derived from terrorist activities, economic and financial crime related offences or the properties the value of which corresponds to such proceeds.

¹⁰ Uchegbu Callista Ukamaka & Kelvin Ibobo, supra, at P. 113

¹¹ Paul Chibuikwe Ezebuilo, supra, at note 3

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D. The adoption of measures to eradicate the commission of economic and financial crimes, and etcetera.

The Commission has the power to cause investigation to be conducted as to whether any person, corporate body or organization has committed an offence under the Act or other law relating to economic and financial crimes. The Agency can equally cause investigations to be conducted into the properties of any person if it appears to the Commission that the person's life style and extent of the properties are not justified by his source of income.¹²

The Economic and Financial Crimes Commission Act, 2004 specifically created the categories for acts or omission that should be criminalized. Sections 14–18 makes special provision for offences relating to financial malpractices in banks or other financial institutions. Under section 16, any public officer who is to discharge of his duty makes to another public officer any false information in any material particular commits an offence. Section 17 of the Act makes punishable any person who retain control of the proceeds of a criminal conduct or an illegal act for another person, whether it is done by concealment, or removal from jurisdiction, transfer to nominees or otherwise. Especially where it is known or suspected that the person has been engaged in a criminal conduct.

A person who without lawful authority engages in the acquisition, possession or use of property that such property loan derived from any offence referred to in the section or engages in the management, organization or financing of any offence under this Act or engages in the conversion of transfer of property knowing such property to have come from any offence under the Act, or even gets involved in the concealment or disguise or the true nature source, location, disposition, movement, rights, with respect to ownership of property where there is knowledge that such property was derived from an offence, commits an offence and this carries an imprisonment term of not less than fifteen (15) but not exceeding twenty -five years.

The menace of corruption in Nigeria and lack of effectiveness of the existing institutions to fight corruption led to the establishment of anti- corruption legislations. These Acts makes comprehensive provisions to prohibit the laundering of the proceeds of a crime an illegal act, provide appropriate penalties and expands the interpretation of financial institutions. It also provides scope of supervision of regulatory authorities on corrupt activities among others. The establishment of these institutions has contributed significantly in combating crimes within the regime of economy and finance as well as government institutions.

¹²Recently the Court sitting in Adamawa State and in line with its powers during the prosecution by the EFCC officials, of the former Governor of Adamawa state James BalaNgilari ordered the forfeiture of the properties of the Governor on grounds that the properties constituted proceeds of corrupt practice. See generally TVC News broadcast at 7pm.

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Interestingly, in all these cases none of the culprits is currently being detained or serving jail term apart from Chief James Ibori, the former Governor of Delta State who has been jailed in the United Kingdom. Given this scenario, where these offenders are allowed to go scot free by employing presently the procedure known as and called “plea bargaining.” Corruption therefore, has grown to become a lucrative business in the country.¹³ Also in a situation, where people steal billions of naira and after their arrest and prosecution such persons are only jailed for three (3) or six (6) months makes corruption in Nigeria the most lucrative business in the world.

3. Challenges and prospects to the institutional effectiveness of the EFCC

There is need to evaluate the challenges and prospects of operational effectiveness of the EFCC in Nigeria.

3.1 Challenges

Beyond legislative measures adopted, the country has consistently occupied one of the top most positions among the most corrupt nations in the world. The persistence of the problem is an indication that constitutional approach and socio-economic reforms have proved to be inadequate panacea to the problem. Based on the foregoing, there is ample need to further explain the protracted and complicated resolution of fight against corruption, apart from the theoretical elucidation that has been earlier reviewed.

The evidence of the ineffectiveness of the anti-corruption legislations in Nigeria can be explained on the ground that, throughout Africa, in spite of laws prescribing stiff penalties for corrupt practices, there is evidence to prove that more money than ever is being stolen from the public treasuries by corrupt means. This trend is obvious from the dockets of the various anti-corruption agencies. The Economic and Financial Crimes Commission established in 2004 has the jurisdiction to prevent, investigate, prosecute and penalize a host of economic and financial crimes, including money laundering and fraud. The penalties for these offences range from long years of imprisonment to asset forfeiture and hefty fines.¹⁴

¹³ It was maintained in Chapter one that the officials charged with the responsibility of enforcing the anti-corruption legislations stand a good chance of enriching themselves in the course of combating corruption.

¹⁴ See the Economic and Financial Crime Commission (Establishment) Act, 2004; See also Folashade B. Okeshola, Corruption as Impediment to Implementation of Anti-Money Laundering Standards in Nigeria, *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 2012, Pp. 78, 90

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The EFCC has recorded significant successes but there is little evidence that public officials or prominent private sector operators feel constrained by the law in their abuse of power and position.¹⁵ A glance through the EFCC's classified 'High Profile Cases' leaves a definite impression of the ineffectiveness of concerned laws in Nigeria. The High Profile role is comprised of cases regarding financial misappropriation and fraud involving billions of dollars.¹⁶ The evidence shows that corruption, hitherto considered to be a secretive and victimless crime, is becoming more brazen and more directly hurtful to easily identifiable victims. In fact, external observers of the African scene, including integrity monitors and development partners, have expressed frustration at the little progress made thus far in the fight against corruption in Africa.¹⁷

Scandals involving theft or misappropriation of ever-more unimaginable amount of National assets have been dominating media reports.¹⁸ These events occur as citizens agonize over graft-induced decline or lack of improvements in living standards. Leaders are conscious of the magnitude of corruption in their countries and the challenge that it poses to development aspirations. Given this awareness, these leaders threaten and cajole their citizens at every opportunity. However, there is lack of congruence between word and action,¹⁹ and it continues to be a painful social experience in these countries.²⁰

Drawing attention from the above, it is apposite to maintain the fact that harrowing experience of law's divergence from social and political forces. As a matter of fact, law would become ineffective when it is out of alignment with social and political forces; this probably begins to explain why despite frequent proclamations of a desire to eradicate corruption, African leaders, have demonstrated a lack of political will in that regard. Some have explained this divergence by the

¹⁵ Thompson Reuters /Aspatore, Understanding Anti-Corruption Issues in Africa: An In-dept look at Recent Developments and Upcoming Trends (2010) available at

<<http://www.trust.org/dotAsset/3fcf9dfe-8662460b82ba869af95db219.pdf>> (accessed 09/29/2014)

¹⁶ Available-at:

<http://www.efccnigeria.org/index.php?option=com/docman&task=docview&gid=15&itemid=82>
(Accessed 29/09/2014).

¹⁷ This is largely due to the fact of political connections.

¹⁸ See, for example: Forum for African Investigative Reporter (FAIR), Pirates, Smuggler, and Corrupt Tycoon Social Bandits in Africa (FAIR Dossier, January 2011); Global Witness, 'International Thief: How British Banks are complicit in Nigerian corruption (October 2010).

¹⁹ For instance, the House of Representatives has in this year 2025 summoned the NNPC to account for over \$17B of sales of crude oil and gas unremitted to the federal account during the Late President Buhari's administration.

²⁰ See for example, BBC News, 'Fine Worlds, but Corruption Soars,' BBC Focus on Africa Magazine, 2nd January, 2006 available at: <<http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/africa/4511746-stm>> accessed 28/09/2014). See also K. Nweze, War against Corruption: NoSacredCows says FG' *ThisDay Newspaper*, February 2, 2011, P. 98

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personal and informal nature of politics in Africa.²¹ As a matter of fact, citizens have begun demonstrating a wide margin of tolerance for corruption, and are often ambivalent about it.²²

Corruption in Africa rests on a complex of social and cultural issues which citizens are often powerless to resist. From the perspective of consumers of administrative services, for example, corruption provides a way to manage and overcome uncertainty. As far as the relationship between the public service and the citizen is concerned, the uncertainty is permanent, and it derives from many factors, principal among which is the impenetrability of administrative regulations and the almost, endless possibilities for manipulation of same by the officials. Another important factor is the ever-present pressure on individuals to meet social obligations, referred to in some of the literature as ‘over-monetization’ of social relations. This pressure makes the need for money a constant reality for everyone in position of authority or leadership.

Some writers have described the hold of corruption on the African society as a ‘vicious cycle.’ According to Blundo and Olivier de Sardan, the fact that the citizen is surrounded by so much unpredictability makes it rational for him/her to take protective measures: ‘on some occasions, it will be possible to benefit from relations, friends, acquaintances, clientele and dependency links, on others it will be necessary to bring protection, to pay the ‘price of cola’ and ‘grease some one’s palm.’²³ The fact that everyone believes that they must protect themselves against the dysfunction of the public services using favours or corruption means that everyone exploits their personal relationship or indulges in corrupt practices all the time.²⁴

In other words, the absence of a moral consensus on corruption deprives the law of necessary social and political synergy for its effectiveness. There are many manifestations of this moral ambivalence towards corruption in the African Society.

Furthermore, this economic inequality in the society explains the legal ineffectiveness in the enforcement of anti-corruption legislations.²⁵ Entrenched inequality militates against a social consensus about corruption and the evils commonly associated with it. For example, research

²¹ See for example, R Joseph, *Democracy and Pre-band Politics in Nigeria: The Rise and Fall of the Second Republic* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1987), P. 112

²² Bratton M, Formal vs. Informal Institutions in Africa, *Journal of Democracy*, 18, 3 (July, 2007).

²³ Blundo G, and Olivier de Sardan JP, *Everyday Corruption in West Africa* in G. Blumdo and J.P. Olivier DeSardan with N.B. Arifari and M.T. Alou, *Everyday Corruption and the State: Citizen and Public Officials in Africa* (London & New York, Zed Books, 2006), 69 at p. 106

²⁴ *Ibid*, at P. 23

²⁵ *Ibid*, at P. 45

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findings indicate that the average African views petty corruption as a morally acceptable adaptive response to inequality.

The common understanding seems to be that petty corruption which is the theft or extortion of small money from the populace by public officials in return for services does not have the capacity to retard the economic progress of the country. Rather, it is the theft or misappropriation of billions of dollars, which are then cached in offshore banks that threatens the economies of African countries. However, the World Bank does not subscribe to this view. In a heavily publicized report published in 2010,²⁶ the Bank castigated the perpetrators of what is called “quiet corruption” in Africa.

Another possible reason for the ineffectiveness in the enforcement of anti-corruption legislation in Nigeria is the lack of implementation capacity. There is overwhelming lack of capacity for the implementation of anti-corruption laws, for example the ICPC and EFCC Acts, have been put forward as an explanation of the persistence of corruption. However, the argument goes, in contexts of pervasive corruption these systems of control are ineffective simply because the benefits of corruption to its perpetrators far outweigh its cost. As a result, there are no ‘principals’ willing to enforce control measures.²⁷

The lack of commitment by high officials of government to the fight against corruption can be explained by the fact that these officials are themselves among the principal perpetrators of corruption. In Africa Ministers of government and the chief accounting officers of the various ministries and agencies are often implicated in scandals involving embezzlement, theft, or misappropriation of huge sums of money from the public coffer. Obviously, the decision of an official not to steal or embezzle would not stop others in similar situation from stealing or embezzling. No meaningful results can be achieved in the absence of coordinated effort by all officials. In the absence of such coordination, the law will be ineffective and routinely ignored with impunity.

There is another possible reason for the ineffectiveness in the enforcement of the anti-corruption legislation is the social influence and the legal Regulation of social meaning. In an attempt to answer the question, why do individuals commit crimes, it will help to explain why the law is ineffective in controlling criminal behaviour. The standard economic conception of deterrence answers this question by postulating that individuals, as rational absorber of self-interests, will commit a crime

²⁶ World Bank, *Africa Development Indicators 2010* (Washington DC: The World Bank, 2010).

²⁷ A. Persson, B. Rothstein & TJ Teorell, *The Failure of Anti-Corruption Policies: A Theoretical Mischaracterization of the Problem*, working paper series 2010:19, ISSN 1653-8919, *Institute University of Gothenburg*, (June 2010), P. 99

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when the expected utility (gain) of law breaking exceeds the expected disutility (loss) of punishment.²⁸ However, there is another explanation that focuses on the effect of social influence and the laws regulating social meaning.

According to this explanation on social influence, which is how individuals' perception of each other's values, beliefs, and behaviour affects their conduct, including their decision to engage in crime, may help explain the persistence of prohibited behaviour.²⁹ Thus 'if individuals perceive that their neighbours are freely dealing drugs or routinely eroding their taxes, or looting public money they are likely to infer that the risks of such behaviours are small and the potential rewards high. The (self-confirming) perception that there is little risk of punishment when large numbers are breaking the law also plays an important role in the dynamics of looting, lynching, and other forms of mob criminality. When a large number of individuals breaks the law without being caught and punished, and when punishment is erratic and mostly incommensurate with the crime, the law becomes ineffective as an instrument of social control. Social influence is strongly explanatory of the pervasiveness of corruption in Africa, just as the ridiculously mild punishment for corruption reflects the lack of clarity in the social meaning of corruption that the law projects. The EFCC should rather focus on silent and careful investigation rather than engaging in media trial. The EFCC should have enough proof before prosecuting, they should lead with evidences. The immunity clause for public office holders should be removed, especially when any of the public office holders is challenged by allegations of corruption and financial crimes. Officials of the EFCC are substantially bereft of plausible and pragmatic standard covers by way of insurance and other likely morale booster in the course of discharge of the official duties. Notwithstanding the above, the EFCC contributes to its inability to be effective in the discharge of its mandate.³⁰

It should also be noted that the activities of the lawyers, judges and the government as represented by the Attorney-General of the Federation, contributed more to the weak performance of the EFCC.³¹ For instance, it was alleged that some members of the Judiciary and senior lawyers have been accused of colluding with the accused in frustrating the trial of high profile corrupt persons. It was observed that the case with which persons accused of crimes like possession of fake currency

²⁸ Jeremy Bentham, *An Introduction to the Principles of Morals and Legislation* (J.H. Burns XH.L.A. Hart, eds.) (London: The Athlone Press, 1970), P. 117; Posner A, *An Economic Theory of the Criminal Law*, 85 *Columbia Law Review*, 1985, P. 1193 and GS Becker, *Crime and Punishment: An Economic Approach*, 76, *Journal of Political Economy*, 1968, P. 169.

²⁹ L. Lessig, *The Regulation of Social Meaning*, 62, *University of Chicago Law Review*, 591, 1996, P. 114; DM Kahan, *Social Influence, Social Meaning and Deterrence*, *Virginia Law Review*, Vol. 83 No. 2 (March 1997), P. 349-395

³⁰ Uchegbu Callista Ukamaka & Kelvin Ibobo, *supra*, at note 2

³¹ *Ibid*, at p. 159

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are prosecuted and convicted within few weeks, while endless delays are granted to accused persons, in high profile corruption cases at the behest of the lawyers.³² Most Nigerians think that senior lawyers are too attracted to money to be made from defending highly corrupt persons to the extent that some of them were totally without inhibition.³³ For example, it was reported of the incidence in which six Senior Advocates of Nigeria at an Abuja High Court were scrambling to appear for six suspects arraigned before an Abuja High Court on a 16 counts charge of stealing N32.8 billion.³⁴ In addition, the activities of the EFCC in the prosecution of cases in court have also been called to question.³⁵ As it has been proven that the EFCC is fond of filing for amendments of the charges against accused persons after their arraignment on the basis to which lawyers to the accused persons always use the opportunity to ask for adjournments to enable them study and respond to the new charges.³⁶

3.2 Prospects on institutional investigations by the EFCC

There are possible reasons for the effectiveness of legislations, premised on the fact that the effectiveness of any anti-corruption legislations will indeed depend on a number of factors alien to the law. The establishment of the EFCC is a very positive step in the fight against corruption and corporate financial crimes.

The vast majority of investigations instituted by the EFCC is a positive step in combating corruption, corporate financial crimes as well as cybercrimes.³⁷

4. Conclusion

The author has demonstrated the fact of establishment of the EFCC as a desideratum to combating the dire consequences and concomitant erosion of the bond as well as benefits of social goods of the Nigerian human society. The demonstration further extended to the implications of checking corruption and corporate financial crimes in Nigeria. The desirability of sustaining the EFCC has been justified in comparison with the daunting challenges associated and always confronting the

³² Ibid, at p. 160

³³ Ibid

³⁴ Ibid.

³⁵ Cf., to the Airport incident involving one female passenger Emmanson Comfort and the Akwa Ibom Air, which attracted immediate arraignment by the Hon. Minister for Aviation in less than 24 hours.

³⁶ Uchebun Callista Ukamaka & Kelvin Ibobo, The Role of the EFCC in prosecuting corporate financial crimes in Nigeria, *supra*, at note 2

³⁷ With respect to the role of the EFCC in Nigeria, see generally, Uchebun Callista Ukamaka & Kelvin Ibobo, The Role of the EFCC in prosecuting corporate financial crimes in Nigeria, at note 2

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17021755

EFCC. The Nigerian society is a huge society in flux physically in undaunted with spiral challenges of development in technology, more particularly, corruption, public office holders sense of entitlement to steal public funds, the menaces of cybercrimes as well as corporate financial crimes. Flowing from the above, there is need to sustain a virile and dedicated, pragmatic and effective investigation based institution to remain abreast of the criminally minded public officials and citizenry.

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